

STUDY ON JUVENILE DELINQUENCY AS LOSS OF MENTAL HEALTH: CONCERNING THEIR EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT IN WEST BENGAL

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Abstract : Our society's future human resources are its juveniles. The goal of this research is to examine how juvenile delinquency affects human capital management, which results in significant societal losses. The juvenile offenders from the Juvenile Detention Center outside of Kolkata were used in the study. In order to determine the juveniles' sociodemographic background, secondary data were gathered from reputable sources and combined with primary data obtained using a closed-ended questionnaire subjected to t-tests and one-way ANOVA analyses. The essential result, which is the horrifying discovery that the greatest rate of offenses comes soon after the age of sixteen, has been formed based on the information gathered and its analysis. The proportion of learned delinquency is significantly higher than the rate of uneducated delinquency. The findings have the potential to broaden society's understanding in order to stop the degradation of upcoming human capital and acquire a useful resource for social advancement. The government must act quickly to prevent young brains from being spoiled in order to reduce juvenile criminality by implementing the right human resource management policy, according to the current study.

Index Terms - Juvenile Delinquency, Social Development, Human Capital, Human Resource Management.

1. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY :

There are many different intrinsic traits that lead to juvenile delinquency in grown-ups children, including adolescents. For this reason, aggressive behavior ranging from misbehavior to such crimes that are punishable in court is referred to as juvenile delinquency. In addition, it is noted that the values of violence, crime, and delinquency are all the same; the only variable that varies is age, which is typically linked to a lower degree of physical and mental development than that of an adult. Different elements of the social environment give rise to various forms of misbehavior that fall under the definition of delinquency. In the justice system for children, juveniles are classified as delinquents rather than criminals, and their punishment is less harsh than it would be in the adult system. This is due to the juvenile justice system's emphasis on building, restoring, and rehabilitating rather than punishing. Compared to earlier times, juveniles have a lower likelihood of remaining in the system.

2. PRESENT SCENARIO :

There is currently ample evidence that the reason for the growing number of juveniles residing at the Juvenile Detention Center in Kolkata is their involvement in anti-social activities. The rising juvenile crime rate is a sign of declining sustainable development. Adolescents occasionally commit crimes as a result of external influences. It is the waste of a resource for the future. Thus, the purpose of this study was to look into the social and educational background variables that are most frequently linked to juvenile delinquency

in the city of Kolkata and the neighboring areas. The new study is significant because it will help manage the societal issue and uncover key elements that contribute to the prevalence of delinquency. This research of the social patterns of today's delinquents in Kolkata and the surrounding areas and future human resources was therefore driven by the need for a comprehensive understanding.

3. BRIEF REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE :

According to a study by **Chattopadhyay, M., and Chatterje, D.(2018)**, on the influence of socio-educational profile on juvenile delinquency in the Kolkata region, victims with a secondary education are more vulnerable and delinquent juveniles from urban areas commit more crimes than those from rural areas. When **Nath, A., & Bandyopadhyay, S. (2016)** worked with migrant children in three homes in West Bengal who were in dispute with the law, they found that more male juveniles than females were involved in this type of crime, and that the majority of reported criminal cases were from the urban area surrounding Kolkata. The phrase "juvenile systems and its criminality in India experiencing obstacles from both society and self" was created by **Haque, H.U. (2012)**. The phrase "youth should receive colleges and universities at correctional home" was first used by **Barton, P.E. (2011)**. The government or private sector ought to provide financial support for educational programs for prisoners. According to research by **Monk-Turner, E., & Oleson, J. (2009)**, there is a gender difference in criminal offenses among high IQ individuals, and unethical actions are essentially the same in juvenile males and females. **Mavroveli, Petrides, Shove, and Whitehead (2008)** conducted research in London, UK, focusing on measuring children's trait emotional intelligence. Positive behavior as judged by teachers was positively correlated with trait emotional intelligence. In their study, **Nichols, T.R., Graber, J.A., & Botvin, G.J. (2006)** examined the gender differences in overt violence and delinquency among middle school students from urban minority groups. They discovered that females were more likely than boys to exhibit aggressive behavior. Boys had a higher percentage of delinquency than did girls. Lower class adolescents were less likely to conduct assault, school delinquency, and public disruptions, according to research by **Ozabay, O., & Ozcan, Y.Z. (2006)**. Males from the middle class are unusual when it comes to social delinquency. According to **Snow, P.C., & Powell, M.B. (2005)**, offenders are less skilled at presenting stories than non-offenders. Delinquents lost their ability to tell stories through language. In New Hampshire, **Brackett, Mayer, and Warner (2004)** investigated the EI's capacity for measurement using criteria, incremental validity, and discrimination. According to the study, women had higher overall EI scores than men. At the school level in London, UK, **Petrides, Frederickson, and Furnham (2004)** investigated the relationship between trait emotional intelligence and deviant conduct as well as academic achievement. The relationship between trait EI and academic success and cognitive ability was inverse. In a study, **Liau, A. Liau, AW. Teoh, and Liau, M. (2003)** shown that among Malaysian youngsters, emotional intelligence was favorably connected with academic achievement and negatively correlated with violence. Emotional perception and controlling the emotions of others were shown to be statistically distinct from other pertinent measures in Australia, according to **Ciarrochi, Deane, and Anderson (2002)**. The understanding of the relationship between stress and juvenile mental health was largely dependent on emotional intelligence.

4. OBJECTIVES :

- A. To investigate the differences in delinquent behavior between young people with and without education.
- B. To investigate how juvenile delinquent conduct varies throughout three consecutive age ranges.

5. HYPOTHESES:

- 5.1. **Ho_A** : There would be no significant difference in juvenile delinquent behavior between those with and without education.
- 5.2. **Ho_B** : There would be no significant difference in the youngsters' delinquent behavior throughout the course of three successive age ranges.

6. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY :

6.1. **AREA:** The study's target sample consists of juvenile offenders from four distinct juvenile prison facilities located in three districts in West Bengal, India: Kolkata, Hooghly, and Howrah. Three homes—the Dhrubashram Home in Ariadaha, Kolkata; the Sukanya Home in Salt Lake, Kolkata; the S M M Home in Liluah, Howrah; and the Destitute Home in Uttarpara, Hooghly—were used for this study. (Fig:1 & Fig:2)

6.2.SAMPLE SIZE: Over 40 delinquent juveniles, both boys and girls, between the ages of 12 and 18, from various socioeconomic backgrounds, participated in the study.

Fig: 1

Fig: 2

6.3. SAMPLING TECHNIQUES: Here, the survey method was used. A closed-ended questionnaire was used in conjunction with an interview to gather information in order to assess delinquency.

6.4. SAMPLING TOOL:

Ho_A : Data analysis was done using the significant t-test computation.

Ho_B : One Way Analysis of Variance computations had been used to analyze the data.

7. DATA ANALYSIS :

7.1. Ho_A : There would be no significant difference in juvenile delinquent behavior between those with and without education.

Chart 1

The outcome shows that, the p-value of two tailed test is 0.22 (Table 1) which is less than the critical value at 0.05 level of significance ($\alpha = 2.14$). So the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis. The data concludes that there is no significant difference of delinquent behavior occurs between educated and uneducated juveniles while the sample mean score indicates that the educated juveniles having more delinquent behavior than the uneducated one (Chart 1).

7.2. **H_{0B}** : There would be no significant difference in the youngsters' delinquent behavior throughout the course of three successive age ranges.

Chart 2

The outcome shows that, the F-value is 1.27 which is less than the critical value of F (3.55) (Table 2) at 0.05 level of significance. So the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore it can be concluded that there is no significant difference of delinquent behavior occurs in three consecutive span of age by the juveniles. The data table shows the ascending values of mean score of delinquent behavior occurs by the juveniles in three consecutive span of age (Chart 2).

8. INTERPRETATION :

Juveniles with less education tend to be more controlling than those with education. The results of this study show that the juvenile offenders were both educated and illiterate. Based only on average scores, the findings indicate that a greater proportion of educated respondents had been found guilty of sexual offenses and cheating, whereas those with less education were found to have committed these crimes less frequently. If these are taken as random variables, then it can be said that educated delinquent behavior occurs far more frequently than ignorant delinquent behavior. The current study indicates that going to school may be associated with a higher likelihood of participating in delinquency. Only 22.5% of illiterate juveniles were judged to have committed crimes, compared to 77.5% of school-age children who were found to be delinquents. Nonetheless, the results show that while the remaining respondents were not enrolled in school at the time of their imprisonment or conviction, almost 3/4 of the respondents were. According to the report, 16 is a sensitive age for juvenile arrest. The maximum age at which juvenile victims occurred was approximately 16 years old. The age at which unethical behavior begins to develop is fourteen years old. Delinquency at this age range has historically been associated with peer groups and activities.

9. CONCLUSION:

Social background patterns that are linked to such delinquencies and negatively impact our human resources include educational attainment, family structure, and moral beliefs. In a broader sense, we must stop the misuse of intelligence. Gaining a fundamental understanding of these elements' routes will help you address some of the issues and delinquencies they cause. For the juveniles to receive meaningful and beneficial rehabilitation and training based on expected outcomes, a proper human resources management program is required. This will be accomplished by implementing an adequate intervention program and raising societal awareness. The foundation of the country is the youth. The entire country will vanish if the pillars are harmed. It was imperative that we adopt a well-designed social framework in order to preserve and replenish our human capital and ensure the long-term prosperity of our country. Since schools are tiny versions of society, the continual practice of human resource management will therefore positively impact social profiles and enhance attention to positive social structures and academic work. In summary, different doors are just waiting for the young people to open them. Since juvenile offenders have potential in many areas, we should maintain them in mainstream schooling while working to lower the rate of juvenile criminality. We must support their interests since doing so will make our country healthier.

10. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE SCOPE :

There are certain limitations to the current investigation. First, there is not enough data in the sample size to fully comprehend the juvenile offenders' socioeducational background. Second, only the juvenile inmates of the juvenile prison facility close to Kolkata are the subject of this study. It would have been possible to take into account other populations with perhaps differing viewpoints. Third, a self-structured questionnaire is used in the study. Response bias is thus a possibility, as well as non-reaction bias. The restriction points to the potential areas of more study, specifically those that may be contributing causes to delinquency.

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